

Leadership and Management in Policing are Best Served by Shared Leadership, Transformational Leadership and Transactional Leadership Strategies

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Abstract:- In this essay, we examine how management and leadership in the police are best served by shared leadership, transformational leadership and transactional leadership strategies, as well as by using a different management strategy as a matter of epistemic practice. Our goal is to determine whether a practice-based approach, which is an alternative to normative management models that have dominated the management literature, can advance our understanding of police leadership. The normative approach frequently focuses on how police leaders should lead as well as on the qualities and abilities of police leaders. The article is divided into two sections. Our attention, on the other hand, is on what leaders do and why they do it, and what, in turn, makes up their professional leadership practices. The first portion examines the historical background of police leadership, policing leadership, the theoretical framework of the study, qualities of a perfect leader, and characteristics of an effective police leader. The second section examines these traits of police leaders as two sides of the same coin: shared leadership, transformational leadership, and transactional leadership tactics. Theorists contend that our research approach would be valuable in complementing more conventional leadership. We examine the ongoing daily dynamics of police leaders' and employees' relationships and practices as well as how these processes constitute leadership practices. Police officers emphasize the value of being able to talk to and address issues with their bosses and co-workers because policing is a team effort. They work primarily in pairs. As a result, being accessible is crucial to the role of a police leader. Every day, one must choose between being loyal to one's own unit and workers while still paying attention to delivering what the centralised entities demand. Police leaders establish a routine in which they consistently strike a balance between their personal standards of leadership and those of their superiors as well as those of the entire organization.

Keywords:- Police leadership, Leadership as practice, Police culture, Police reform.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Pearson-Goff and Herrington (2014), Fleming (2015), Flynn and Herrington (2015), Filstad et al. (2018), and Karp et al. (2018), the manner in which police leaders lead and how they develop their leadership practices beyond what others consider to be good leadership have received little attention to date. In general leadership

literature, which is predominated by normative leadership models of what leaders should do, the question of how leaders actually perform everyday leadership is rarely addressed. These normative models are at best problematic and at worst naive because they ignore social and cultural connections and how leadership must be understood in relation to specific circumstances and all the complexities that go along with them (Alvesson 2017; Day 2014).

There are numerous instances of studies that isolate particular police leaders from police leadership practices while ignoring the cultural and structural contexts and what the leader-follower relationship is like within these practices (Pearson-Goff and Herrington 2013; Fleming 2015; Pfeffer 2015; Carroll 2016; Raelin 2016). Instead, traditional leadership work (Carroll et al. 2008; Crevani and Endrissat 2016; Dovey et al. 2016) has concentrated on the unique characteristics, tendencies, and competences of leaders, independent of the leadership situation. Furthermore, the majority of leadership research is still reliant on behavioral self-reporting questions (Riggio 2019; McCusker et al. 2019).

The literature on police leadership also emphasizes how to enhance the individual police leader as opposed to the relationships between the leader and followers, without taking into account the context of policing, its structure, or its culture (Bratton and Malinowski 2008; Eterno and Silverman 2010; Cockcroft 2014; Pearson-Goff and Herrington 2014; Flynn and Herrington 2015; Haake et al. 2015).

II. THEORETICAL FRAME WORK

This study adopted the Great Man theory evolved around the mid-19th century. The Great Man theory assumes that the traits of leadership are intrinsic. That simply means that great leaders are born they are not made. This theory sees great leaders as those who are destined by birth to become a leader. The trait leadership theory believes that people are either born or are made with certain qualities that will make them excel in leadership roles. That is, certain qualities such as intelligence, sense of responsibility, creativity and other values puts anyone in the shoes of a good leader. In fact, Gordon Allport, an American psychologist, "...identified almost 18,000 English personality relevant terms" (Matthews, Deary & Whiteman, 2003: 3). Behavioral theory also incorporates B.F. Skinner's theory of behavior modification, which takes into account the effect of reward and punishment on changing behavior. An example of this theory in action is a manager or leader who motivates desired behaviour by scolding employees who arrive late to

meetings and showing appreciation when they are early or on time.

III. CONCEPTUALIZING LEADERSHIP IN THE POLICE

In police, there are four types of leadership: senior, operational, individual, and organizational. To be successful in their role, law enforcement personnel must possess leadership traits. At the operational level, effective incident management and teamwork are crucial. The task is different at the senior level since it is more strategic while yet containing elements of command. Systematic management, direction, and administration of a service are all aspects of organizational leadership. To promote fit-for-purpose police leadership in an evidence-based, ethical profession serving a diverse, democratic society, we must first outline desired attributes in an ideal police leader.

The opinions expressed for this review indicate that the ideal police leader is someone who is motivated by the essential principles of policing, seeks out challenge, and is fast to adapt; furthermore, someone who is able to comprehend and take advantage of technology's advantages and sound business practices. An effective leader is one who empowers, believes in, and encourages each person to succeed among their peers, in their teams, and throughout their organizations; one who manages the challenges posed by new criminal activity and issues with public safety; one who values diversity and difference; and one who readily accepts personal responsibility while maintaining the confidence of communities. These are the types of leaders who exhibit resilience in dealing with challenging circumstances and adapting to them without sacrificing their other qualities. A communal style of leadership is present in many successful organizations, even while no one leadership style or model can be stated to represent the entire solution to future challenges. This leadership style puts the leader in the position of a facilitator who ultimately supports the team. Power might be distributed to all levels and improved two-way communication under a more communal leadership paradigm.

After describing these traits, we must assist leaders in navigating new career routes while acknowledging the need to get the best out of people through proper assistance, accountability, and rewards and recognition that are practical. According to this analysis, funding for leadership development is uneven, and in times of financial hardship, training in the non-cognitive "soft" skills that are essential to leadership can be the first to be reduced. But if we want to successfully handle upcoming demands, we must have the best leadership available. What if you invest in growing your personnel and they leave is a worry expressed by some. What if you don't invest in them and they stay.

In their book *Leadership for Health Professionals*, Ledlow and Coppola (2011) note that there are many definitions and variations of definitions in the literature and offer the following collection of definitions of leadership from different authors:

- Tannenbaum, Weschler, and Massarik (1961), leadership is the exercise of interpersonal influence in a situation and is geared towards the accomplishment of a specific goal or goals through the use of communication
- Stogdill (1974), leadership is the establishment and upkeep of structure in expectations and engagement.
- Peter and Waterman (1982), leadership is the process of directing an organization toward success.
- Rauch and Behling (1984), leadership is the process of directing an organized group's activities toward the accomplishment of a goal.
- Jacobs and Jacques (1990), leadership is the process of giving a collective endeavor a goal (meaningful direction) and inspiring willing effort to be exerted to attain that aim.
- Yukl (1994) observed that the majority of definitions of leadership reflect the idea that it entails a process of social influence in which one person intentionally exerts influence over others to organize the interactions and relationships in a group or organization.

The leadership definitions listed above were combined by researchers like Ledlow and Coppola (2011) to create a new definition. "Leadership is the dynamic and active creation and maintenance of an organizational culture and strategic systems that focus the collective energy of both leading people and managing resources toward meeting the needs of the external environment using the most effective, efficient, and efficacious methods possible by moral means," according to the definition of leadership provided by the Harvard Business Review."

Tannenbaum et al. (1961), Rauch and Behling (1984), and Yukl (1994) all defined leadership as "influencing." One of the key elements of leadership, according to Tannenbaum et al. (1961), Peter and Waterman (1982), and Jacobs and Jacques (1990), is guiding. Leaders should encourage and motivate their followers to realize the vision. The goal should be a common goal that the leader inspires everyone to work toward. A practical definition of leadership is to motivate, direct, and influence others as necessary. Burns (1978: 425) reiterates his broad concept of leadership multiple times throughout his enormous volume, but it is maybe best stated in the conclusion. In a situation of rivalry and conflict, leadership is the reciprocal process of mobilizing different economic, political, and other resources by people with specific aims and values in order to achieve either independent or shared goals shared by both leaders and followers.

It's important to note that both transactional and transformative leadership are covered under the broad term. The definition is lengthy and may contain too many variables for scholars or practitioners to utilize it practically. But in order for others who followed after him to more easily synthesize the essence of leadership, he consolidated some important aspects of it. These components are: (1) reciprocal process; (2) resource mobilization; (3) competition and conflict; and (4) shared objectives.

IV. OPERATIONALIZATION OF THE VARIABLE OF LEADERSHIP

A. DIMENSIONS OF LEADERSHIP

In a systemic view of leadership, there are fundamentally three components: influence, direction, and inspiration.

B. INSPIRE

According to Ledlow and Coppola (2011), the leader is in charge of motivating staff members to be loyal to the organization, and his inspiration, motivation, excitement, and outstanding communication skills are vital in this regard. According to Ledlow and Coppola (2011), leaders must convey a vision to their team members in order for them to understand how certain circumstances and events could be crucial. The word "inspire" has a number of definitions in the Pocket Oxford English Dictionary (2007).

The first is defined as "[giving] [someone] the desire to act," and the second is defined as "[a] person or thing that inspires." Collaborate, congratulate, contribute, and connect are all listed under the element of "inspire" in the Seijts and Crim (2006) list of the 10 C's. Employees believe that working as a team with the trust and cooperation of their

team members is more efficient than working as an individual or with a team with weak ties, according to Seijts and Crim. They go on to say that outstanding team builders create a supportive environment that encourages cooperation and trust. The eighth "C" stands for "collaborate" in this sentence. According to Seijts and Crim, "Congratulate," the fifth "C," is where employees are recognized by the excellent leader.

According to Seijts and Crim, the sixth "C," "Contribute," is when people want to realize that their opinions matter and that they are significantly influencing the success of the business. Under the first "C," "Connect," leaders must show that they value their team members, according to Seijts and Crim. Statements like "My leader is a team builder," "My leader recognizes my accomplishments within the organization," "My leader helps me see and feel how they are contributing to the success and future of the organization," and "My leader shows that he/she values me as an employee" are used to measure this dimension. Table 2 goes into more detail about the components and claims of the dimension "inspire."

Table 1: The elements and statements of the dimension called "Inspire"

ELEMENT	STATEMENT
Collaborate	My leader fosters teamwork.
Congratulate	My boss commends me for my contributions to the company.
Connect	My boss demonstrates that they value me as a worker.
Contribute	My boss aides me in understanding and appreciating how they contribute to the accomplishments and future of the company.

C. GUIDE

The leader's job is to provide appropriate leadership to the team. According to the 2007 edition of the Pocket Oxford English Dictionary, a "guide" is "a person who gives advice or points other people in the right direction." Confidence, credibility, clarity, convey, and career are "guide" components that fall within the 10C's of Seijts and Crim. According to Seijts and Crim in 2016, effective leaders foster a culture of trust within an organization by serving as role models for high ethical and performance standards. The reputation of a corporation should be upheld, and leaders should act with integrity (ibid.). The letter "C," which stands for "Credibility," neatly sums up this idea. Clarity of purpose, desired outcomes, and how employees may help the organization accomplish them are all mentioned by Seijts and Crim as being essential. This third "C" is called "Convey" (ibid), and it denotes the leader's responsibility to make clear what is expected of the team members while giving them feedback on their performance. Because of this, effective leaders set up

systems and procedures that help individuals do crucial jobs and advance their goals.

It is clear that employees want to be creative. The same is true for employee career growth. According to Seijts and Crim (2006), who support this claim, leaders must offer hard, meaningful work with the chance for professional progression. This is classified as "C" for "Career." Statements like "My leader helps to create confidence in a company by being an example of high ethical and performance standards," "My leader strives to maintain a company's reputation and demonstrate high ethical standards," "My leader clearly communicates the organizational vision," "My leader clarifies his/her expectations of me as an employee," "My leader clarifies his/her expectations of me as an employee," and "My leader provides feedback on my functioning in the organization" are used to measure the guide dimension. Table 3 provides more information on the components and claims of the dimension "Guide."

Table 2: The elements and statements of the dimension called "Guide"

Element	Statement
Confidence	My boss serves as an example of strong ethical and performance standards, which fosters confidence in a company.
Credibility	My boss works hard to uphold the reputation of the business and exhibit great moral principles.
Clarity	My boss explains the organization's crystal-clear mission.
Convey	My boss explains what is expected of me as an employee and gives me feedback on how I'm doing at work.
Career	My boss offers hard, fulfilling work with chances for professional advancement.

D. INFLUENCE

One of the fundamental elements of leadership is influence. According to the definition of "influence" in the Pocket Oxford English Dictionary from 2007, it is "the ability to have an impact on someone's beliefs or actions," which implies that a leader has power over his or her

employees. According to Seijts and Crim (2006), the seventh "C" (Control) is something that employees appreciate, allowing the leader to give them opportunity to exert this control. Statements like "My leader sets the boundaries which cater to the needs of the employees as well as the organization" are used to measure "influence."

Table 3: lists the elements and statements of "Influence"

Element	Statement
Control	My leader establishes the limits that serve the needs of the organization and the workers.

Three leadership styles are suggested by Saks and Gruman (2014) as having the potential to affect employee engagement through psychological circumstances, job resources, and job expectations. The three categories are leader-member exchange, empowering, and transformational. According to Hogan and Kaiser (2005), effective team performance is encouraged by competent leadership, which enhances the wellbeing of the occupants. According to Seijts and Crim (2006), effective leaders continually work to improve employee abilities and produce little victories that will assist the team, unit, or organization operate at its peak. Bad leaders, according to Hogan and Kaiser (2005), lower the standard of living for everyone they are responsible for. Hogan and Kaiser (2005) go on to say that the ineffective leader is to blame for the extreme unhappiness of individuals who work for him or her.

According to Gallup (2013a), an excellent manager engages his or her staff in a variety of ways while showing a sincere interest in them. The manager can foster a healthy and open work atmosphere by developing strong, trustworthy relationships with their employees, giving them a sense of support and participation. Great managers care about individual performance while investing in talent, according to the Gallup (2013a) research. According to Hewitt (2015), leaders are the ultimate architects of an engaged workplace culture and that leadership is a driver of employee engagement.

The explanation is that they hold the opinion that "leadership is what makes or breaks the projects." Seijts and Crim (2006), two organizational behaviour experts, offer intriguing insights through the notion of the "10 Cs for employee engagement;" The 10 Cs for employee engagement are primarily focused on what company executives can do to boost employee engagement.

Table 4: Leadership

LEADERSHIP CHARACTERISTIC	LEADERSHIP FOCUS
1. Connect	Employee engagement is a direct indication of how workers feel about their connection with their manager, thus leaders must demonstrate their appreciation for their workforce.
2. Career	Most people desire to take on new challenges at work. Consequently, leaders should: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Provide possibilities for career advancement together with difficult and meaningful work. ✓ Make people answerable for advancement. ✓ Assign objectives ✓ Offer positions that are enhanced by responsibilities and obligations.
3. Clarity	A clear vision must be communicated by leaders.
4. Convey	Leaders make clear what is expected of them and give their team members feedback on how they are doing inside the company.
5. Congratulate	Leaders should acknowledge others, and they frequently do so.
6. Contribute	People may see and feel how they contribute to the success and future of a company with the support of a leader.
7. Control	Boundaries are established by leaders to meet the demands of both the organization and the workforce.
8. Collaborate	Great leaders establish teams and cultivate an atmosphere that encourages cooperation and trust. Thus, the development of teams should be a concern for the leaders.
9. Credibility	The reputation of a corporation should be upheld, and leaders should act with integrity.
10. Confidence	Good leaders set an example for the organization in terms of high moral and performance standards.

Source adapted: Seijts and Crim (2006), Dharmasiri (2011).

E. POLICE LEADERSHIP

The literature on police leadership has also increased the conceptualization of managerial orientation (Bratton and Malinowski 2008; Eterno and Silverman 2010; Pearson-Goff and Herrington 2014; Flynn and Herrington 2015)

while focusing more on the individual police leader than their leadership. Great leaders excite and inspire their team members to put up more effort toward accomplishing the common objective (Fenwick & Gayle, 2008). Leaders encourage team members to contribute beyond their

personal goals and match team goals with organizational goals (Burns 1978). They also support the team's goals and vision. This affirms the significance of leadership style and how it affects staff engagement as well as employee motivation and satisfaction.

The culture of an organization is believed to be driven by its leaders (Mintzberg, 2013). Leaders create subcultures via their example of behavior, values, and leadership. Employee commitment and attitude are impacted by the subculture of the organization, according to analysis that found that employees are more likely to identify with a subculture that has been shaped by their leaders (Lok, Westwood, & Crawford, 2005).

F. CHARACTER OF ANEFFECTIVE LEADER

The character factor, according to Thompson, Grahek, Phillips, and Fay (2008), is the one that has received the least attention in recent leadership studies despite being crucial to understanding significant leadership failures. Leadership character includes a leader's moral and ethical objectives, beliefs, and actions (Bass, 2008). As a result, character can be excellent or poor, with virtues making up "good character" (Palanski & Yammarino, 2007). These qualities can be measured and observed in psychological processes and traits-like characteristics (Peterson & Seligman, 2004). There are three types of character that can be distinguished with regard to leaders: locus, transmission, and reception (Hannah & Avolio, 2011). The internal characteristics of a leader, such as his or her personality, values, moral reasoning, and identity, were described as the locus of leader character. The behavior the leader uses in any circumstance is referred to as transmission, or the leader's behaviors.

Reception refers to how the targets of leadership (i.e., subordinates) interpret those signals. Reception comprises what is seen, how it is understood, and the explanations observers give for whence certain behaviors originated. By asking subordinates about their leader's character, this is often measured. The focus of the current doctoral dissertation is on honesty and modesty, as well as the pairing of forgiveness and modesty in the first and second articles, as well as the pairing of thankfulness and concern for and interest in subordinates in the first article. The definitions of these five elements in the context of leadership are provided next.

The following five examples illustrate why character matters in leadership practice and why it shouldn't be ignored in leadership research. Power must be utilized in all types of leadership; the question is not whether it will be used, but rather whether it will be used effectively and wisely. Alternatively, "When talking about leadership, we must ask ourselves, 'Leadership for what?'" (Gini, 2004). Bennis (2007). We must include character in the leadership equation because power causes people to lose their inhibitions, act according to their own preferences and aims, objectify others, and develop narcissistic tendencies (Maner & Mead, 2010).

Second, the sheer volume of confusing inputs that senior executives encounter has a significant impact on how they understand events, make judgments, and behave (Hambrick & Mason, 1984). Therefore, it is necessary to disprove the assumption that character might be overlooked so long as leadership involves decision-making procedures. Third, leaders establish a climate by their actions and decisions, which are symbolic representations of their beliefs, motivations, and worldviews (Kaiser, Hogan, and Craig, 2008). Schein (2004), who claimed that deliberate role modeling is one of the key embedding strategies by which leaders develop, sustain, and occasionally change their group culture, provides confirmation of this claim. Fourth, understanding human behavior requires observation.

Weiss (1977) offered an illustration of the organizational setting. He discovered that the degree of leadership style resemblance between superiors and subordinates depended on how successful and competent the supervisors were seen by the latter. By witnessing and copying the behavior of leaders and other people in their workplaces, followers can learn about ethical situations (Brown & Trevio, 2006). Last but not least, the actions of leaders effectively convey what is crucial and how followers ought to act (Neubert, Kacmar, Carlson, Chonko, & Roberts, 2008).

For instance, it is more probable that followers will think and act in a similar manner if leaders convey by their speech and behavior that it is vital and acceptable to be egocentric and to battle for one's own aims. Thus, we must adopt the perspective that character matters because it influences not just the behavior of leaders but also, eventually, that of their subordinates. According to Manz and Sims (1981), followers' behavior and wrongdoing are significantly shaped by what they learn from watching how leaders behave. Two quotes from Bennis (2007: 2) are worth quoting for the fifth reason why character cannot be ignored in the leadership equation: "Corporate leaders have almost as much power to shape our lives, for good or ill." and "Leadership affects the quality of our lives as much as our in-laws or our blood pressure."

G. CHARACTERISTICS OF A LEADER

Qualities of Exceptional Leaders The author will list the qualities discovered to be crucial for successful executive leadership as a consequence of this study. In addition, the author plans to: (a) analyze these unique traits (whether innate or learned); (b) provide justifications for why these traits are necessary for effective leadership (according to thought-leaders like Bass, Bennis, Kouzes, & Posner); and (c) make use of theories and definitions that have already been discussed in this study. This will enable agreement or conflict on whether leadership results from nature or nurture.

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The author observed findings that were eerily similar to those of Kouzes and Posner (1993) in a significant portion of the literature analyzed for this investigation. According to the author, many of the conventional traits advocated by leadership specialists (including Bass, Bennis, and Burns) are in fact necessary for effective leadership. In stark contrast to this idea, McCall (1998: 16) makes the claim that "everyday experience, which shows that effective leaders come in various shapes and sizes, denies the assumption that all successful leaders have one set of a dozen or so characteristics or behaviors." According to McCall (1998), leaders are created via experience rather than being naturally endowed with it.

In their engaging book *Credibility*, Kouzes and Posner (1993) align their thoughts with those of Phillips (1992). According to Kouzes and Posner's (1993) analysis of more than 1,500 managers across the country, integrity is the key component of effective leadership. The 225 values, traits, and attitudes that these managers listed as being essential to leadership were then dissected and categorized into 15 categories by a group of researchers. According to the study's findings, the most common response given as the quality that makes a good leader is integrity.

➤ *Integrity*

According to Maxwell (2011: 35), integrity is sadly becoming increasingly rare in today's society because "personal standards are crumbling in a world that has taken to the hot pursuit of personal pleasure and shortcuts to success." A true leader, according to Bennis and Nanus (1989), is honest with himself, especially about himself, recognizes his strengths and weaknesses, and confronts them head-on. Teal (1996) goes one step further in the *Harvard Business Review on Leadership* (1998) when he asserts that integrity in management entails being accountable, speaking plainly, maintaining one's word, and being aware of oneself. Trust grows and strong connections flourish when followers believe their leader is honest and moral.

According to *Leadership: A Quick and Easy Guide* (Birkett, et al., 1999: 95), which builds on the ideas of Kouzes and Posner (1993), Maxwell (1993), and Phillips (1992), "leaders with integrity are renowned as those who always can be relied upon to do what they say. Leaders will carry out their plans of action, and a colleague or friend may rely on them for support when needed. Because a person with integrity stands up for what is right and works to avoid unethical or unfair behavior, integrity appears to be a learned trait. In accordance with Birkett, Daum, and Southworth (1999: 95), "employees who value these qualities tend to gravitate toward organizations that value them, and these same employees tend to be highly productive."

➤ *Self confidence*

Although Danzig (1998) contends that "the one quality they (leaders) have in common, and without which anyone who tries to lead is doomed to fail, is confidence" (p. xv), people still look for their leaders to have a high level of integrity. According to Bass (1990), who did all of the studies and research on leadership, outstanding leaders were unusually characterized by qualities like self-confidence and esteem. This finding is consistent with these ideas. Danzig (1998) adds that if you are confident in who you are, what you are doing, and the organization you are working for, other people will be aware of it. They will adhere to you (page xv).

According to Kouzes and Posner (1993), leaders should learn a specific lesson on confidence. The members of the group will suffer greatly and lose respect for the leader's abilities to inspire and guide the team if leaders feel they are unable to complete a task, even when they have the necessary skills to do so. In such cases, leaders have no business attempting to lead a group. Roberts (1987) wrote that: People in leadership positions who exhibit a lack of confidence in their abilities to carry out leadership assignments give signals to their subordinates, peers, and superiors that these duties are beyond their capabilities and may become weak leaders (contributing to Kouzes and Posner's (1993: 20) argument). According to Birkett, Daum, and Southworth (1999: 66), a leader needs to be confident in themselves. Because "no one can be expected to know everything" and "the same degree of confidence does not transfer to every situation," according to these authors, being confident does not imply that you have the answers to all the questions.

As stated by Thornton (2001: 2), "building confidence is accomplished by affirming people's talents, recognizing good performance, and providing ongoing education." According to Kouzes and Posner (1995), who concur with Thornton (2001), leaders must treat individuals in ways that increase their self-confidence so they may accomplish more than they first thought feasible. The study of Kouzes and Posner (1995) makes it clear that fostering self-confidence in constituents is a two-way process. Leaders not only have the power to affect the expectations of others; they also have the power to affect the behaviors of their followers. In conclusion, this author concurs that self-assurance is necessary for both successful leadership and effective follow-up. Followers must endeavor to accomplish the goals set forth by the leader, and leaders must foster an environment of positive reinforcement or rewards for excellent behavior.

According to McCall's (1998) research, successful leaders tend to exhibit a success syndrome. In a study of successful people, it was discovered that those who performed well on an early assignment were rewarded with more difficult work, which raised their self-esteem and confidence. Furthermore, having difficult jobs pushed successful people to go further, develop their skills, and form new connections. People who are confident typically achieve some level of success in life, but excessive confidence can be harmful in positions of leadership.

Overconfidence "can lead to cockiness, poor judgment, and Insensitivity to the situation or to others," say Kouzes and Posner (1993: 262), which will erode trust and ultimately destroy a team. All of these situational occurrences aid in the growth of strong leaders.

➤ *Energy*

The next noteworthy trait of leaders is introduced to leadership practitioners by DuBrin's (1998) ideas. According to DuBrin (1998: 47), "the physical factor of energy also sheds light on the nature versus nurture issue". According to Bass (1990), leaders frequently exhibit a high degree of activity in a range of circumstances. Along with these concepts, it is clear that some people are biologically predisposed to having more energy than others. But it won't help someone become a good leader unless they are able to channel their energy effectively.

The research of Bass (1990) enables individuals studying leadership to comprehend how a leader's energy affects them. In his revolutionary book *Handbook of Leadership*. According to Bass (1990: 63), "leaders were also characterized by a high rate of energy output". According to numerous experts. The article "What Leaders Really Do" by Kotter (1990), which was published in the *Harvard Business Review on Leadership*, integrates the concepts of Bass (1990) and DuBrin (1998). Kotter (1990: 48) emphasizes that success always necessitates "an occasional burst of energy" in this essay. There are similarities between Conger's (1992: 21) suggestion that this energy surge might have "some genetic roots" and DuBrin's (1998) theory.

Bass (1990: 81) continues this research of energy by stating that after approximately 25 investigations, it is clear that leaders are typically "endowed with an abundant reserve of energy, stamina, and ability to maintain a high rate of physical activity." A high level of energy and an amazing degree of vitality were found to be the first shared attribute in a review of the growth and careers of world-class leaders. Leaders require more physical stamina than the majority of their team members in order to focus and work more diligently.

Interestingly, "highly successful leaders tended to exhibit a high rate of energy output" (Bass, 1990: 81), even when physically challenged or in bad health. Tom Peters, a leadership expert, recently shared his insights on energy in a recent issue of *Fest Company* (2001). Highly effective leaders have the passion and energy necessary to move their teams and businesses forward. According to Peters (2001), energy is the driving force behind every successful business, team, and initiative.

The *Leader within You* by Danzig (1998) provides leadership researchers with crucial traits necessary to effective leadership, whether in business or in daily life. Passion is a big force, says Danzig (1998) in a powerful way. Leaders often discover their passion while pursuing a goal. It is not only being committed to a purpose or exercising diligence. They are consumed with a passion as they work toward a goal. Its heat is tangible. Following

leaders who are passionate about what they do inspires followers to support them in achieving their goals.

Effective leaders are able to mobilize employees within their companies or corporations, as well as clients, vendors, business partners, shareholders, and anybody else who can support the cause. Without leaders transforming chores into crusades, thrilling adventures, or deeper objectives, nothing worthwhile is ever accomplished. In essence, any of us may be born with a passion. To expect to achieve extraordinary corporate goals, leaders must be able to nurture their passions and inspire change for success.

➤ *Character*

Moving on to a second crucial trait of successful leaders, it is clear that character is just as important in a leader as skill. It is not enough for a leader to do things well; he must also do the right thing, claim Bennis and Nanus (1989: 30). To efficiently lead organizations, leaders need to have this attribute, which is the core of character. Kouzes and Posner (1993: 80) add on Bennis and Nanus' (1989) ideas by stating that "people who have acquired the skills to put their beliefs into practice possess the moral capacity to achieve good ends with good means."

Everyone wants to follow leaders who have enough moral integrity to act morally uprightly while under pressure and challenges and still perform well and consistently. According to Badaracco (1998: 89) in the *Harvard Business Review on Leadership*, leaders encounter multiple "defining moments" that "ask executives to dig below the busy face of their lives and refocus on their core values and principles."

According to Badaracco (1998), defining moments ultimately add up over time to form the very foundation of a person's character. A leader's personality and credibility are established through the process of character formation, which takes a lifetime. In accordance with the ideas of Badaracco (1998), Bennis and Nanus (1989), and Kouzes and Posner (1993), Danzig (1998) conveys that a leader's character motivates followers to attain objectives without compromising principles. Danzig (1998) argues that leaders act morally and refrain from taking quick cuts that compromise ethics. Danzig (1998: 87) expands on this idea by proposing that a leader sets an example by consistently showing his subordinates that there is a value system in place that is attached to the leader's leadership. The operation's value system is a crucial element.

The leader's persona is the source of the energy that permeates the space and inspires pride. Leaders serve as role models. They encourage dedication and foster admiration and respect for the organizational ideals that form its core. Most people have heard at some point in their lives that adversity develops character. A person's character and being are tested during trying times. People only establish themselves as leaders through challenging situations, which is regarded as a fostered trait. An ineffective leader will exhibit a lack of character, and their leadership will ultimately lead to the failure of organizations.

➤ *Decision-making*

Business executives are aware that it might be challenging to put decisions that have a significant influence on an organization into practice at times, according to Phillips (1992). An executive leader's ability to make judgments that are crucial to the organization or the group depends on their confidence and expertise. When he writes that "a problem is defined and isolated; information is gathered; alternatives are set forth; an end is established; and a means is created to achieve that end; a choice is made," Burns (1978: 379) simplifies the process of decision-making.

Decisions are repeated in ever-finer detail as a result of this continuous process of improvement. Decisions are repeated in ever-finer detail as a result of this continuous process of improvement. According to Phillips (1998: 97), "the atmosphere is dynamic and vibrant in a corporation with decisive leaders" because "people tend to move with a spring in their step and purpose in their direction." Abraham Lincoln was aware of the significance of effective executive decision-making in any firm. Lincoln's exceptional decisiveness allowed him to make decisions, effect change, and win the war.

Roberts (1987: 103) shows that "every decision" involves some risk" as he continues to discuss executive decision-making. Due to insufficient experience, risk is increased when a leader is aware of the possible effects their choices could have on the entire organization. Decision quality and decision acceptance are two aspects that influence decision-making, according to DuBrin (1998). While "decision acceptance refers to how committed group members are to implementing a decision effectively," according to DuBrin (1998: 147), "decision quality refers to the objective aspects of a decision that affect group or individual performance."

Both forms of decisions are evident in our daily lives. For instance, when a leader must pick between five alternative paper providers for a copier machine, decision quality is typically not a significant concern. Any brand of paper in the appropriate grade will do the trick. In order for a decision to be accepted by the group, each individual must be "strongly committed to implementing a decision made by the leader because it is in their self-interest" (DuBrin, 1998: 147). The purchase of laptops for sales representatives by a manager would be warmly adopted by the workforce since they believe it will raise commissions and productivity. The end result is that before making a specific decision for the business, the leader must take into account both the short-term and long-term effects. According to Burns (1978), a significant decision that the executive leader must make that is pertinent to a clear purpose activates a decision-making system. a culmination of several of the traits stated above, including confidence and honesty

➤ *Communication skills*

A leader must be able to explain decisions to constituents as they are taken in order to achieve goals. Before looking for examples of communication, it is crucial to comprehend what communication is in its most basic form. Effective

communication is often defined differently by different people. This is why it is stated in Conrad and Poole's (1998: 5) definition of communication: "Communication generally is defined as a process by which people, acting together, create, sustain, and manage meanings through the use of verbal and nonverbal signs and symbols, within a particular context."

To put this term into the context of executive leadership, Bass (1990: 673) states that "the way a manager communicates with colleagues and subordinates is an important aspect of his or her leadership style." One's success in becoming a leader depends on the caliber of their talk docs. According to Birlett, Daum, and Southworth (1999), one of the fundamental leadership skills, communication ability, plays a significant role in a person's overall effectiveness as a leader. Even if one has exceptional visionary powers, if one cannot properly articulate their ideas, others will not, and in fact, cannot, buy into their vision for the future. Every interaction a person has with a member of a certain organization provides a chance to involve them in its higher purpose and overall strategy.

➤ *Vision*

Vision is a key keyword in leadership. Kous and Posner (1995: 95) define vision as "an ideal and unique image of the future" in their book *The Leadership Challenge*. Additionally, according to DuBrin (1998), vision is the capacity to see various and improved circumstances as well as the means of achieving them. Top executives have a crucial task: vision creation. Because of this, Bennis and Nanus (1989: 41) are adamant that a guiding vision is the first essential component of leadership. The leader has the fortitude to persevere in the face of obstacles, including failure, and a clear vision of what he wants to accomplish both professionally and personally. You cannot possibly go there unless you know where you're going and how to get there. Leaders are oriented and concerned about the future of the company they work for. Constituents might strive toward a certain purpose or target by developing a vision. The leader must have a clear vision for the future, say leadership experts Kouzes and Posner (1993: 16), since "they must have a destination in mind when asking us to join them on a journey into the unknown."

V. LEADERSHIP TRAITS

Compared to older ideas that saw features as solely hereditary characteristics, the present notion of leadership qualities is broader. The proper definition and meaning of the term characteristic are not without controversy, though (Day & Zaccaro, 2007: 104). "Relatively stable and coherent integrations of personal characteristics that foster a consistent pattern of leadership performance across a variety of group and organizational situations" is how Zaccaro et al. (2004) define leader attributes. According to Zaccaro et al. (2004), these traits are a reflection of a variety of consistent individual variances that encompass both cognitive ability and other personality traits. Yukl (2006) claims that the word "trait" is used to describe a wide range of personal characteristics, such as personality traits, needs, reasons, and values. Personality traits are rather consistent propensities to

act in a certain way. Self-assurance, extroversion, emotional maturity, and energy level are a few examples.

A desire for particular stimuli or experiences is referred to as a need or motive. Psychologists typically distinguish between social wants like success, prestige, connection, power, and independence and physiological requirements like food and shelter. Because they direct, energize, and maintain behavior, needs and motives are significant (Yukl, 2006). Values are internalized attitudes about what is good and bad, moral and immoral, and ethical and unethical. Examples include excellence, courtesy, loyalty, fairness, justice, honesty, freedom, equality, and justice. Values are significant because they affect a person's preferences, issue perceptions, and behavior choice (Yukl, 2006). According to evidence, learning and an innate propensity to find satisfaction in particular stimuli or experiences work together to determine traits (Bouchard, Lykken, McGue, Segal, & Tellegen, 1990). Learning presumably has a greater impact on some features than others, such as morals and social demands (Yukl, 2006).

A reduced number of widely defined categories have been sought after in an effort to streamline the development of trait theories due to the proliferation of personality traits that have been discovered over the previous century (Yukl, 2006). The Five Factor Model of Personality, also known as the Big Five Model, is one such attempt (Digman, 1990; Hough, 1992; Judge et al., 2002). The taxonomy includes extraversion, conscientiousness, agreeableness, emotional stability, and openness among its widely defined qualities.

The use of this taxonomy by leadership academics to simplify the interpretation of findings in the extensive and complex literature on leadership attributes has grown in recent years. However, not all academics concur that taxonomies with more specific features are preferable to the Big Five model of personality (Yukl, 2006). Only four of the Big Five traits extraversion, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and openness had non-trivial relationships with leadership emergence and effectiveness, according to the largest meta-analysis to date conducted by Judge et al. (2002).

VI. POLICE PRACTICE

An alternative to the traditional leadership literature that instructs leaders on what they should do in order to lead effectively is the leadership-as-practice approach to leadership studies (Arnulf and Larsen 2015). In a practice-based approach, the emphasis is on the day-to-day practice of leadership, how actors 'get on' with the task of leadership, as well as the emergent and dynamic processes of these practices (Whittington, 2006; Chia and Holt 2006; Crevani and Endrissat 2016; Dovey et al. 2016).

The literature on police leadership has also increased the conceptualization of managerial orientation (Bratton and Malinowski 2008; Eterno and Silverman 2010; Pearson-Goff and Herrington 2014; Flynn and Herrington 2015) while focusing more on the individual police leader than their leadership. Numerous significant studies on police leadership have used transformational leadership as their

foundation (Fleming 2015), but the preference for transformational leadership over transactional leadership neglects to take into account policing situations (Cockcroft 2014).

Shared leadership redirects attention away from the individual leader and onto the community context since it is founded on collectivism, collaboration, and involvement in a holistic manner (Gronn, 2002). However, in situations involving distributed leadership, the quasi-militaristic rank structure in policing leadership and the 'rank knows best' power dynamics are disregarded (Steinheider and Wuestewald 2008; Silvestri 2011; Davis 2018). The empirical research on police leadership by Caless and Tong (2015) paints a picture of how strategic leadership is now practiced in Europe. However, we discover that the leadership-as-practice approach is more thorough, as it investigates leadership as an emergent phenomenon in the intricate and dynamic processes of the development of relationships between leaders and employees in specific contexts and practices (Day et al. 2014; Uhl-Bien and Ospina 2012; Gardner et al. 2010; Avolio et al. 2009; DeRue and Ashford 2010).

It's important to recognize leadership as a group effort (Crevani and Endrissat 2016; Dovey et al. 2016). When leaders and followers work together to make sense of a situation and create methods to relate to one another and act (Cunliffe 2001; Shotter and Cunliffe, 2003), that is what practice looks like. The practice of leadership thus emphasizes the connection between leadership and social and cultural constructions that are relational and collective, situated and culturally defined, as well as material and emotional (Chia and Holt 2006; Raelin, 2016). Because practice leads both leadership activities and people involved, the approach addresses the simultaneity of practice (Schatzki 2001; Nicolini 2012). Leadership is the practice itself.

Furthermore, according to Law and Urry (2004), Kjellberg and Helgesson (2006), Pye (2005), and Smircich and Morgan (1982), a leadership-as-practice approach primarily relies on the practitioners' perception of reality and their ability to interpret it. Pye (2005) refers to sense-making in action as Weick (1995) notably recognized that sense-makers' perceptions of both their internal and exterior environments are linked and dynamic. With practitioners serving as the unit of analysis and practices serving as connections in action, the evolving dynamics of practices are underlined by the use of verbs like "belonging," "understanding," and "knowing" (Gherardi 2012; Gherardi and Strati 2012). Practice is "what persons say, imagine, conceive and produce, and think while attempting to carry out these activities," according to Nicolini (2003:7).

According to Whittington (2006) and Orlikowski (2010), a practice is the culmination of all customs, norms, and processes for thinking, acting, and behaving. Therefore, "zooming in" entails examining cultural dynamics, cognitive and experiential processes, as well as behaviors connected to a shared understanding of reality; in contrast, "zooming out" entails examining the function, scope, and goals of

structures, politics, the profession, bureaucracy, and the state, all of which must be taken into account in order to comprehend the practice (Nicolini 2012).

A. Leadership Style

The majority of people in a variety of sectors have found success to be a result of effective leadership. A clear vision and understanding are given to the followers by the leadership (Yukl, 1998). There are primarily two categories of leadership positions. Democratic leadership is the term used for the first role. Additionally known as transformational leadership. Transactional or autocratic leadership is the other function (Lussier, et al. 2001). A visionary democratic leader is sensitive to his followers' demands. It aids followers in becoming more capable of contributing to decision-making.

An authoritarian leader, on the other hand, directly controls events without consulting his people (Avolio, 1999). The people in a company who create the tone and culture are known as leaders. According to Northouse (2004), leadership is the process through which one person persuades a group of people to accomplish a shared objective. An effective leader may influence their followers to accomplish the organization's objectives. Managers and leaders can be distinguished from one another with ease. Leaders bring about change and inspire their team members, whilst managers establish order and stability. In order to develop a relationship with his or her followers, a leader must have respect for the character traits of people who are prepared to devote their time and abilities to achieving common goals (Bass, 1985). To describe the attributes, characteristics, and styles of many leaders and leadership philosophies have developed over time (Bass, 1985).

B. Self-Efficacy

According to research, persons who have high levels of self-efficacy view problems as opportunities, are very dedicated to the tasks they complete, and put more time and effort into their daily routines (Bandura, 2001). Self-efficacy has proven to be a strong motivator and well-being predictor in the context of healthcare professionals, such as nurses (Munir & Nielsen, 2009). Future cooperative organizational performance approaches are supported by it (LeBlanc, 2010). The main personal resource for understanding intrinsic motivational processes like work engagement is self-efficacy beliefs.

C. Reward and Recognition

In any discussion of employee engagement, recognition is at the center. Awards, whether monetary or not, as well as simple acknowledgement of good performance are all examples of recognition. Whatever the approach, recognition systems have several elements, such as communication and respect that are all crucial for maintaining high levels of employee engagement.

When a business or manager recognizes a team, they convey a clear statement about the kinds of endeavors and accomplishments the business values. The organization is encouraging the efforts and attitudes it appreciates in its staff by showing its appreciation in this way. For an engaged

employee, earning appropriate recognition or rewards is crucial because poor recognition or rewards can lead to burnout (Bhattacharya & Mukherjee, 2009; Maslach, Schaufelli, & Leiter, 2001). The responsibilities and descriptions offered by the company and the expectations of the employees occasionally seem to differ noticeably (Bhatnagar, 2007).

The staff believes that incentives are crucial to keeping them interested in their companies. As a result, the company should support employee self-development, training aimed at improving their skills, and participation in specific official or unofficial activities in order to foster a positive work atmosphere and increase their productivity.

D. Trust

According to Cummings and Bromiley (1996), trust is the confidence of one person or group that another person or group will make an attempt to maintain promises, will be honest, and will not take advantage of the situation at hand. According to Golembiewski and McConkie (1975), the factor having the greatest ability to affect individual and group behavior is trust. Understanding the factors that affect team trust may therefore be crucial to encouraging team effectiveness. To be more precise, team members' behavior-focused leadership tactics can serve as audible cues to other team members that they are making an attempt to keep their end of bargains, are trustworthy, and don't abuse their position as team leaders (Cummings & Bromiley, 2000).

VII. LEADERSHIP STRATEGIES

The success of any organization is greatly influenced by the leadership style. A leader's manner of giving instructions, carrying out strategies, and inspiring followers to achieve objectives is referred to as their leadership style. The word "style" refers to a leader's capacity to sway his subordinates. Leaders support others and themselves in making the correct decisions. They establish a course, develop a motivating vision, and produce something fresh. Leadership is dynamic, engaging, and inspirational since it involves determining where you need to go in order to "win" as a group or an organization. Understanding various leadership philosophies and how they affect employees' job performance is the goal of this essay.

VIII. SHARED LEADERSHIP

First, shared leadership has been promoted as a strategy to increase team effectiveness in recent years by scholars and practitioners. Ramthun and Matkin (2012), for instance, claimed that shared leadership is frequently advantageous since followers are more likely to follow the individual who has the best knowledge and abilities rather than relying entirely on the traditional leadership style's vertical influence process. In fact, numerous additional empirical research have shown that shared leadership teams produce superior team effectiveness (Pearce and Sims, 2002; Wang et al., 2014; Serban and Roberts, 2016). We must note, though, that this isn't always the case. This large and beneficial association was not supported by Fausing et al. (2013) or Mehra et al. (2006), and Boies et al. (2011) even discovered that shared leadership has a detrimental effect on

team effectiveness. Such ambiguous results highlight the need for additional empirical data. As a result, the initial goal of our research is to specifically look at the relationship between shared leadership and team success in order to further our understanding of the benefits of shared leadership. The degree to which teams live up to organizational expectations is how we define team performance in this study (Essens et al., 2009). This frame of view motivates us to consider team efficiency from a variety of angles. As a result, we adopt the viewpoints of Aube and Rousseau (2005), Balkundi and Harrison (2006), and Mathieu et al. (2008), who analyze team performance from two unique perspectives: team task performance and team viability. Team viability is the ability of teams to retain their members and function effectively over time, whereas team task performance is how well the group achieves (or even surpasses) job objectives (Balkundi and Harrison, 2006).

Second, unsolved questions must be addressed in order to develop a more detailed understanding of the effects of shared leadership. The effectiveness of the time relevant modifiers should be properly investigated. Researchers have underlined that shared leadership is a dynamic, emergent, time-varying construct (Avolio et al., 2009) that is influenced by task features as well as team environment (Carson et al., 2007; Wu et al., 2020). Therefore, ongoing changes in the inputs, procedures, and outputs of various project life cycle stages may have an impact on the development of shared leadership in teams as well as its link to team performance (Wu and Cormican, 2016). The effectiveness of shared leadership may be moderated by the project life cycle, although this has not been extensively theorized about or practically evaluated. In order to provide insights into the boundary conditions surrounding when shared leadership is more or less relevant to team success, this significant unfilled gap requires more research. Because of this, the second research objective is to concentrate on the dynamic nature of shared leadership and examine the moderating role that the project life cycle has in the relationship between shared leadership and team effectiveness.

Third, studies focusing on project teams are still scarce and underdeveloped despite the growing interest in the shared leadership area (Scott-Young et al., 2019). Numerous team types, including senior management teams (Singh, et al., 2019), entrepreneurial teams (Zhou, 2016), consulting teams (Carson et al., 2007), and change management teams (Pearce and Sims, 2002), have adopted the shared leadership paradigm. Project team-related inquiries, however, are scarce. There are still very few studies focused on shared leadership theory in the context of project management, despite the fact that the modern workplace is becoming more and more project-centric (Scott-Young et al., 2019). This study investigates the efficacy of shared leadership in project-based engineering design teams in order to increase the external validity of the shared leadership construct in project settings. Project teams are also uniquely suited to explain when shared leadership is more likely to work successfully in teams since they have clear start and end times based on the length of the tasks (Farh et al., 2010).

IX. TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP

The neocharismatic paradigm, which emphasizes the charismatic and emotive aspects of leadership (introduced by Downtown in (1973), includes transformational leadership (Northouse, 2004). According to Avolio (1999), it is a process that alters and transforms subordinates to participate in performance that exceeds expectations.

In at least three different ways, transformational leaders increase their followers' willingness to exert more effort. They first increase awareness of the significance of particular objectives and methods for achieving them. Second, they persuade followers to put the needs of the organization ahead of their own. Finally, they encourage and fulfill followers' higher-order wants, such as self-actualization and self-esteem (Bryman, 1992). As a result, followers are said to be inspired, energized, and intellectually stimulated by transformational leadership. The several facets of transformational leadership, according to Burns (1978), include idealized traits and behaviors, inspiring motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized focus.

According to Bakker et al. (2011) and Macey and Schneider (2008), transformative leadership, empowering leadership, and leader-member interchange are particularly important for fostering employee engagement. Leaders that are transformational offer a purpose that goes beyond short-term objectives and concentrates on higher order intrinsic needs. In contrast, transactional leaders concentrate on the efficient exchange of resources.

X. TRANSACTIONAL LEADERSHIP

Transactional leadership, according to Bass (1999), is defined by an exchange of value between the leader and the followers. This theory attempts to explain how leadership could occur based on the understanding that leadership does not always lie in a person or circumstance but rather in the social interaction between the leader and the follower (Van Seters & Fields, 1989). Bass and Avolio (1997) characterized transactional leadership in terms of two characteristics: the use of contingent rewards and management by exception.

By promising rewards and benefits in exchange for tasks completed, transactional leaders are able to motivate subordinates and thereby achieve desired results (Bass, 1990). Transactional leaders thrive in less competitive, more stable corporate environments like those found in the world of business before the 1980s (Tichy & Devanna, 1990). To assure the survival and effectiveness of the organization, a new type of leadership, known as transformational leadership, is however necessary in the current cutthroat corporate environment.

In contrast to transformational leadership, transactional leadership does not individualize the needs of subordinates or place a strong emphasis on their personal growth. To advance their own and their subordinates' goals, transactional leaders exchange valuable items with their followers (Kuhnert, 1994). Because doing what the leader

wants is in the best interest of the followers, transactional leaders are powerful (Kuhnert & Lewis, 1987).

XI. LEADERSHIP AND MANAGEMENT

In many ways, the process of leadership is comparable to that of management. Influence is a component of management as well as leadership. Working with people is a requirement for both management and leadership. Effective goal attainment is a concern for both management and leadership. In general, many management duties are actions that fall under the definition of leadership that we provided at the beginning of this section. Leadership, however, differs from management in other ways. Aristotle is credited with the study of leadership, but management did not begin to exist until the turn of the 20th century, when our industrialized society began to take shape. In order to help companies work more effectively and efficiently, management was developed. Fayol (1916) was the first to identify the four main management tasks as planning, organizing, staffing, and controlling. These tasks still serve as exemplars of the management discipline today.

Kotter (1990) stated that the roles of the two are very different in a book that contrasted the roles of management and leadership. Organizational order and stability are management's key concerns, whereas change and movement creation are leadership's top priorities. While leadership seeks adaptive and positive change, management seeks order and stability. Major management activities differ

significantly from those of leadership in how they are carried out. Kotter (1990: 7-8) argued that management and leadership are both crucial for an organization to succeed, despite the fact that they differ in scope. For instance, if a company has excellent management but lacks leadership, the result may be oppressive bureaucracy. On the other hand, if a company lacks management but has strong leadership, the result could be meaningless or poorly targeted change. Organizations must support both skilled leadership and competent management for success.

In addition to Kotter (1990: 221), many other academics contend that management and leadership are two different concepts. Bennis and Nanus (1985), for instance, insisted that there is a sizable difference between the two. While leading is having an impact on people and developing a vision for change, managing entails completing tasks and mastering routines. In their oft-quoted statement, "Managers are people who do things right and leaders are people who do the right thing", Bennis and Nanus made the gap between the two very plain. Another proponent of separating management from leadership was Rost (1991). Although management is concerned with coordinating efforts to fulfill tasks, he maintained that management is a relationship of unidirectional authority and leadership is a relationship of multidirectional influence. Leaders and followers work together to bring about significant change, whereas managers and employees work together to sell goods and services (Rost, 1991: 149-152).

Table 5: Management and leadership roles

Management Produces Order and Consistency	Leadership Produces Change and Movement
Planning and Budgeting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish agendas • Set timetables • Allocate resources 	Choosing a Course of Action <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a vision • Clarify big picture • Set strategies
Organizing and Staffing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide structure • Make job placements • Establish rules and procedures 	Aligning People <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate goals • Seek commitment • Build teams and coalitions
Controlling and Problem Solving <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop incentives • Generate creative solutions • Take corrective action 	Motivating and Inspiring <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspire and energize • Empower subordinates • Satisfy unmet needs

Source: Adapted from *A Force for Change: How Leadership Differs From Management* (pp. 3-8), by J. P. Kotter, 1990, New York: Free Press.

XII. LESSONS LEARNED THROUGH LEADERSHIP

A. Lesson 1: Allocate Sufficient Time for Leadership

Although this advice might seem to be obvious, both I and those I have watched have overestimated the time needed for several leadership positions. When leaders discover they are unable to fulfil the demands of their roles due to a lack of time, difficulties arise. Organizations that don't have enough time for leadership struggle to function effectively and accomplish their goals; leaders and others who care about the organization start to worry about how well it will run. Members of these organizations frequently create substitute decision-making processes that get around

the absent leader. As a result, there are communication issues and organizational concerns.

Time must be set aside for both scheduled activities and unforeseen emergencies, or for quick resolution of issues. These unforeseen issues can arise at any time, frequently at the worst possible moments. A leader must set up regular time slots for their leadership duties while maintaining flexibility in the rest of their schedules to deal with these unforeseen issues. I advise leaders to regularly and explicitly assess how much time they should devote to their leadership duties. Even if the amount of time they predict is greater than what they will be able to provide, this exercise can help them arrange their calendars.

These projections can draw knowledge from experiences of the leaders formulating them as well as from those who have held similar roles. These time estimates should go beyond the bare minimum, but due to external constraints, they frequently fall short of the whole amount of time that leaders would prefer to have available. The difference between the desired amount of time and the amount of time that is acceptable for leading businesses is substantial.

B. Lesson 2: The Need for a Different Mind-set in Leadership

In our work as physicians, researchers, and educators, we aim for near-perfection. Despite the fact that we are typically rather close to perfection, we judge our own performance and that of our co-workers by determining how far we still have to go. We frequently overlook the fact that we mostly succeeded in achieving our goals during this process. As an illustration, consider the evaluations of our publications before they are published or the reviews of the cases we present during grand rounds. It is crucial that we make an effort to offer the best clinical care or the most precise new information to other professionals. We have shown via our qualifications, education, and experiences that we are capable of achieving high levels of technical expertise. We gradually come to expect this level of performance from ourselves, and unless we try to cram too much into the time we have available, we nearly always meet it. This expectation, in my opinion, applies to all highly technical professions as a whole, not just to doctors and other healthcare workers.

On the other hand, leaders must develop the capacity to understand that not all of the areas under their control will attain levels that are equivalent to these technical criteria. Organizations have limited resources, which, in my opinion, are never sufficient to carry out all of their objectives. The leader's time and dedication, the workforce's abilities, political reality, and financial resources are a few examples of these constraints. In these situations, a leader's job is to allocate resources in a way that maximizes the accomplishment of the corporate missions and goals. Some of the organizations' operations, like any health care they render or the accuracy of their bookkeeping, will need to adhere to the strict guidelines of technical specialists. Other activities might only be supported sporadically or not at all. Organizations might limit the number of locations where they offer therapeutic services or give particular functions, like marketing or development, only a limited amount of support.

C. Lesson 3: Delegate More to Get More Done

There is a limited amount of time available for leaders to address all of the problems within their businesses. If they don't delegate, their organizational roles are only as broad as what they can individually accomplish. I've observed departments with few successes as a result of the chairmen's inability or refusal to assign tasks to their employees. There are several causes for this. In one instance I saw, the department chair believed that if the chair acted as an example for faculty members, they would automatically take on more responsibility and increase their activities. This

strategy failed because the chair failed to provide the faculty members clear instructions, leaving them in the dark about the fact that she herself did not want to deliver the clinical services. They didn't want to get involved since they truly thought the chair was doing a great job. In this instance, the chair did not comprehend the limitations of modeling without delegation instructions.

D. Lesson 4: The organization is important, not the individual leader

Organizations are there to carry out their goals or missions. These are now typically explicitly designed to direct organizations' activities toward concentrating on the reasons for their existence. Comprehensive strategic plans often incorporate vision and values statements, goals, and objectives in addition to mission statements. These plans can take many various forms.

Strategic plans offer direction for the work of organizations, albeit they should be updated periodically. The elements of strategic plans, aside from the objectives, guide the directions of organizations over a long period of time. By putting their strategic plans into action, leaders must lead their teams to success in accomplishing their objectives.

The activities of organizations ought to be stable and ongoing as a result. New leaders, in particular, should proceed cautiously while changing the organizational orientation. They may have favourite initiatives in mind, but they should only carry them out if they are in line with the strategic plans of their organizations, i.e., continue in the same directions. The process of changing a strategic plan takes involvement from all stakeholders, thus it is unlikely that the focus on the new goals of the leader would happen right away. Organizations, on the other hand, should create their strategic plans to provide their leaders some latitude in selecting goals.

E. Lesson 5: The importance of and complexity in personnel management

I didn't understand the value of an organization's staff or how challenging working with it might be until I had some experience. Here are a few things I noticed. Engage in constructive communication with all employees—internal and external—who have the potential to have an impact on your operations. Organizational support staffs manage the flow of information required for decision-making. They can either help or hinder its processing, and they frequently choose one based on how they feel about the people asking for it. The personnel of organizations outside of your organization may occasionally be involved in approval processes. Internal and external workers alike respond favourably to compassion and respect, often because they don't get enough of it. Too frequently, our co-workers hold employees accountable for delays or inevitable bureaucratic restrictions that are not their fault. Because of this, these employees often receive rude or unfavourable treatment. Treating them well will encourage them to help you with your paper work rather than motivating them to keep it at the bottom of the pile.

When at all possible, provide projects and tasks to people who are genuinely interested in completing them since they will provide the motivation to do so. Multiple operational and strategic tasks must be successfully completed for an organization to be successful. When these initiatives are carried out by co-workers who have a strong desire to see them accomplished, the likelihood that they will be completed effectively is significantly raised. The wise leader will choose colleagues to lead the initiatives that they are passionate about, creating champions who are more likely to put up the effort required for success. Often, a leader will choose one of several projects to work on based on the presence of an enthusiastic champion. "As a leader, devote your efforts to the success of those you lead."

XIII. SUMMARY

Together with the previously mentioned works, Kouzes and Posner (1995) condense the idea that leadership is ultimately a set of abilities, and that any talent can be improved upon with the right motivation and desire, practice, feedback, role models, and coaching. "Leaders learn by leading, and they learn best by leading in the face of obstacles," assert Bennis and Nanus (1989). Leaders are created by problems, just as weather creates mountains. The fundamental training for leaders has included dealing with difficult co-workers, the absence of vision and virtue in the executive suite, uncontrollable external factors, and their own blunders as stated by Bass (1990: 146).

Through considerable research on the subject of leadership, the author has come to the conclusion that in order to become an effective leader, a person needs combine various natural talents with practical leadership experience. In conclusion, Farkas and Wetlaufer (1996: 146) observe that "the debate about personality will persist until scientists discover a gene for leadership - and think of the repercussions that would have in business, not to mention politics." There will always be people who believe that only traditional General Patton types are capable of leading an organization to success, even if science eventually discover that leadership is more a question of nurture than of nature. According to research, leadership is more complex than that and is influenced more by external needs than internal traits (Farkas & Wetlaufer, 1996: 146).

The trait approach to leadership has recently experienced resurgence in the lexicon of scientific leadership research (Zaccaro, 2007). Although the trait- based perspective was virtually rejected for nearly 40 years, over the last few decades, research has succeeded in demonstrating that traits do in fact add to the prediction of leader effectiveness (Judge et al., 2002; Hogan & Kaiser, 2005; Zaccaro et al., 2004). In addition, recent reviews have converged in their identification of a set of stable attributes that have consistently received substantial empirical support as predictors of leadership criteria (Bass, 1990; Zaccaro, et al., 2004; Yukl, 2006; Judge et al., 2009).

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